

Effect of Work Environment and Training on Job Satisfaction through Career Development Mediation

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Abstract

This study aims to determine whether there is an effect of the work environment on job satisfaction. Moreover, this paper investigates whether training affects job satisfaction and if there is an effect of the work environment on career development. It also determines there is there an effect of training on career development in the Ministry of Finance; is there an effect of career development on job satisfaction, is there an effect of the work environment on job satisfaction through the mediation of career development, Is there an effect of training on job satisfaction through the mediation of career. The results showed that the work environment variable impacted job satisfaction, training positively affected career development, and job satisfaction. Career development has a positive impact on job satisfaction. The work environment has a positive impact on job satisfaction through career development. Training has a positive impact on job satisfaction through career development.

1. Introduction

Job satisfaction is important in managing Human Resources (HR) because it directly or indirectly affects work productivity. In the study of organizational behaviour, it is stated that the higher the level of satisfaction of a person at work, there will be more positive feelings about his work. On the contrary, a low level of job satisfaction indicates a negative relationship between an employee and his work (Robbins & Judges, 2013). Organizations with many employees tend to be satisfied at work. This becomes more effective when compared to other organizations with fewer employees (Seema et al., 2021). Following the Memorandum of Service mentioned above, DJPPR has conducted studies and analyses related to job satisfaction as a follow-up to the recommendations of the Inspectorate General's audit findings related to HR management at the DJPPR Secretariat, including: (1) We are conducting employee job satisfaction surveys within the DJPPR environment to obtain constructive input and suggestions related to HR management by the end of 2020; (2) we are conducting studies or analyzes related to the results of the satisfaction survey, including:

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- a. Processing and analyzing survey data on employee job satisfaction at the end of 2020
- b. Identifying follow-up steps related to the survey results.
- c. Presenting the results of the survey and conveying them to related parties

From the study data and analysis of employee job satisfaction obtained from the HR Section of the DGPR Secretariat, the percentage of interest in moving and getting a new work environment was 17.4%, and 45.8% were still in doubt. The rest did not want to move from their current work environment. Concerning the problems faced, the Inspectorate General of the Ministry of Finance hopes that the follow-up to the recommendations given to DJPPR can explore further HR management in employee responses to employee satisfaction levels at work through employee job satisfaction surveys. The satisfaction survey is a means of expressing feelings about the position or work through a work report to find out employees' morals, opinions, attitudes, climate, and quality of work (Mangkunegaran, 2020).

Data from survey results in the DJPPR environment as a follow-up to the recommendations of the Inspectorate General obtained 45.2% answered satisfied, 38.1% answered quite satisfied, and 16.7% respondents answered dissatisfied. The level of dissatisfaction with the work of the first DJPPR employee is Dit. PDPPI with a percentage of dissatisfaction at work of 18.4%, followed by Secretariat employees of 16.7%.

Table 1 Job Satisfaction Study
Study Data Identify the level of job satisfaction at DJPPR in 2020
processed in 2021

No	Echelon II Unit	Satisfied		Enough		Not satisfied	
		Amount	%	Amount	%	Amount	%
1	Secretariat General	38	45.2	32	38.1	14	16.7
2	Dit. PH	26	41.3	34	54.0	3	4.8
3	Dit. SUN		58.7	17	37.0	2	4.3
4	Dit. PS	14	28.0	28	56.0	8	16.0
5	Dit. PRKN	20	52.6	17	44.7	1	2.6
6	Dit. PDPPI	8	21.1	23	60.5	7	18.4
7	Dit. SPP	15	33.3	26	57.8	4	8.9
8	Dit. EAS	26	41.9	28	45.2	8	12.9
Amount		174	40.8	205	48.1	47	11.0

Data processing from the HR Section of the DJPPR Secretariat on the results of the dissatisfaction study shows that the level of dissatisfaction at work will result in the desire to move from DJPPR for various reasons. From the data obtained from the HR Section of the DJPPR Secretariat, dissatisfaction in working at DJPPR is grouped into several reasons, namely career development, workload distribution, facilities and infrastructure, rewards and punishments and others. Dissatisfaction in working in the DJPPR environment is expected to be improvements or changes in managing HR at DJPPR.

Work Environment and Training Variables at DJPPR are independent variables that affect job satisfaction in the DJPPR environment, while career development variables are mediating variables. The work environment is a factor that affects the level of job satisfaction along with the increase in millennial employees, with data from the HR Department providing information that the percentage of millennial employees at DJPPR is above 60%. In dealing with demographic changes, especially millennial employees, to the demands of a comfortable, mobile, fluid and collaborative work environment while remaining oriented to work quality by prioritizing a trust-building, digital environment, it is necessary to take action to change the work environment. From the results of a study

conducted by the HR Department,

The Future Workspace (RKMD) challenges DJPPR in meeting the supporting facilities for the work environment. The provision of supporting facilities for physical work, one of which is the procurement of laptops, is limited to the DJPPR budget and must be planned through a budget proposal mechanism sourced from the APBN. Laptops are very important because of the demands of work that are mobile and without a dedicated seat. The limited ownership of State Property (BMN) laptops is one of the problems in meeting the needs of a comfortable work environment for employees.

Not all are in good condition from the inventory data of State-Owned Goods / BMN Laptops at DJPPR. They need repairs and replacements to meet the needs of employees in supporting work so that it will affect the level of job satisfaction in the organization. Data obtained from the List of State Property Details at the BMN manager found that the number of laptops available was 345 units with two damaged conditions. In comparison, the need for laptops to support the work environment to support the implementation of the RKMD was 504 units. The lack of facilities in this work environment will greatly affect employee job satisfaction.

The activity-based workplace is a strategic transformation in work that gives a choice of space arrangements for activities/business processes that adapt to the characteristics of employees so that the application of the work environment in terms of working space in the form of layout arrangements must adjust to the shared workspace, collaboration room and refreshment room. The purpose and objectives of the Activity-Based Workplace are expected to create a positive, collaborative work environment (eliminate silos both vertically and horizontally), encourage employees to think creatively, be innovative, result-oriented and increase employee job satisfaction.

The standard of work equipment as part of the work environment at DJPPR is guided by the Decree of the Director-General of Debt Management Number KEP-49/PU/2011, which has not regulated the layout of the workspace design based on the ABW concept. Job satisfaction of DJPPR employees, especially for millennial employees. The Circular Letter of the Minister of Finance, number 9/MK.1/2019, is expected to be a piloting guide for the implementation of ABW within the Ministry of Finance, including, in this case, the DJPPR. Not all training planning can be implemented because there is a schedule for cutting the current year's budget.

Table 1
Detailed Operational Instructions for DJPPR Training Activities
Comparative data on initial planning and implementation of internal training
Based on POK for Fiscal Year 2020, processed in 2021

No	planned	Budget	Implemented	Cost
1	<i>Islamic Finance</i>	50,000,000	Retirement Preparation	165,000,000
2	<i>Financial Modeler</i>	43,500,000	<i>Coaching</i>	262,500,000
3	<i>IT Training</i>	225,500,000	Assessment Preparation	225,000,000
4	<i>Project Management</i>	67,500,000	<i>Excellent Service</i>	120,000,000
5	<i>CRMP</i>	153,000,000	<i>CRMP</i>	102,000,000
6	<i>Legal Audit</i>	40,000,000	<i>Chartered Financial</i>	52,500,000
7	<i>CRMO</i>	93,000,000	<i>CRMO</i>	136.400.000
8	<i>Project Financing</i>	130,000,000	<i>Certified Financial</i>	121,500,000
9	<i>CHRP</i>	21,000,000	<i>Bond Market Anl.</i>	66,000,000

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10	<i>Chartered Financial Analyst</i>	52,500,000	ISO refresh	33,000,000
11	<i>Econometrics Time Series</i>	25,000,000	TDP	22,859,000
12	<i>Financial Modeling</i>	75,000,000	Presentation Techniques	20,000,000
13	<i>Certified Public Accountant</i>	34,500,000	<i>Certified Accountant</i>	34,500,000
14	Presentation Standard	120,000,000	Educational Presentation	150,000,000
15	<i>Certified Internal Auditor</i>	29,700,000	PBJ	22,500,000
16	<i>How To Handle Media</i>	90,000,000	IHT Manaj. Risk	27.100.000
17	<i>Certified Securities Analyst</i>	54,000,000	<i>Securities Analyst</i>	67,500,000
18	Internalization of Values	127,448,000		
19	<i>Communication Skill</i>	120,000,000		
20	PPP Internalization	150,000,000		
21	Profiling Training	225,000,000		
22	ISO refresh	112,500,000		
23	<i>English Business</i>	67,500,000		
24	<i>International Trade Finance</i>	50,000,000		
25	<i>Actuarial</i>	50,000,000		
26	<i>Cinematography</i>	30,000,000		
27	<i>Sovereign ALM</i>	50,000,000		
	Total Planning	2.286.148.000	Total Realization	1,628,359,000

Another problem faced by the organization is that the training needs that are urgent because they are needed in the current year cannot be fulfilled because the budget is not yet available. They have to wait for next year because they must be proposed in the Training Need Analysis mechanism in the Human Resources Department. Besides that, another problem in training is that not all employee wishes to become trainees can be fulfilled with various considerations. The training proposal from each employee is facilitated in the re-performance application.

In the career development mediation variable, in the career development mechanism, DJPPR uses the Minister of Finance Regulation number 161/PMK.01/2017 concerning Talent Management as the legal basis and implementation of its policies. The purpose of career development following these regulations is to provide equal opportunities in career development and the realization of self-actualization through career development. In the analysis of the results of the study of satisfaction in working at DJPPR as a result of the recommendations of the Inspectorate General, employees provide suggestions on the suitability of interests/passions with the field of work that is their responsibility. From the data obtained, the percentage of input related to passion considerations in employee placement as part of career development at DJPPR, as many as 70 employees (83%)

Another problem faced in the career development of DJPPR employees is the limited number of target positions to promote employee career development. The limitation of the target position is not proportional to the number of talents and potential talents in the DJPPR, so the opportunity to occupy the target position in the promotion process is very small. In 2020, data from the HR Section of the DGPR Secretariat showed the number of target positions for echelon IV is only nine. For echelon III, it is not available, so the opportunity for employees to be included in the list of candidates for filling the target positions is very small.

Further problem data information related to the level of employee dissatisfaction in working in the DJPPR environment was obtained through a brief interview with the Head of the Human Resources Development Subdivision on October 15, 2021, who said that "secretariat employees only learn about administration and do not learn much about the economy, public policy." which results in work that is not challenging and does not develop much", in addition to the expectations of employees in the DJPPR Secretariat regarding the desire to participate in training according to their wishes, they are very limited because the quota of training participants is adjusted to the training needs of each Echelon III unit. Training needs at the DJPPR Secretariat to meet competency standards at the DGPR Secretariat, which are supporting and administrative.

Further information was obtained from a brief interview with the Head of the Human Resources Career Planning and Development Subdivision on December 15, 2021, who said that career development at DJPPR was carried out through promotions. In the promotion process, there are very limited target positions. In contrast, talented candidates for one target position have very small opportunities for employees at DJPPR because they have to compete with other employees with limited availability of target positions every year.

The implementation of open space at DJPPR as part of the ABW program provides an atmosphere of room layout in a work environment that is not rigid and overcomes the level of boredom at work and closer relations between employees by prioritizing a borderless system between departments within the DJPPR Secretariat and between Sub-directorates in each Directorate in DJPPR. In addition, the limited budget sourced from the APBN has an impact on the limited equipment facilities obtained by each employee, for example, the need for laptop facilities to support the implementation of ABW, which is still lacking, in addition to the need for replacement of old laptops that have started to break down.

In general, the results of short interviews and field observations, the HR Department of DJPPR expects researchers to contribute research outputs to find variables related to employee satisfaction to be taken into consideration by decision-makers in making decisions. In theory (Keith Davis, 2016), job

satisfaction is the compensation received by employees as a return for the work that employees have done for the organization. Several variables that affect job satisfaction include work environment, training and career development. The work environment is attached to employees to get maximum work results and is divided into two parts, namely physical and non-physical. According to (Milhem et al., 2014), training is a series of processes for delivering skills and knowledge needed by employees in supporting the achievement of organizational tasks and functions, which will ultimately have an impact on career development and employee satisfaction levels at work. The organization must carry out career development to prepare for future employee career opportunities and advancements. Appropriate career planning will assist the organization in changing the behaviour and new competencies of employees toward the expected career path (Aguinis, 2013). In previous studies, it was found that if the conditions of the social work environment were conducive, it would increase job satisfaction. The same thing is also found in the implementation of good career development, and then employee job satisfaction will increase. In addition, if the conditions of the social work environment are conducive and the implementation of career development is good, then employee job satisfaction will increase (Nurdini et al., 2019). Training management's role in improving competence by improving training programs within the organization is very significant on the level of employee job satisfaction, especially knowledge indicators. This has been studied due to knowledge-based job satisfaction. (Kianto et al., 2016).

From the results of descriptive survey data in the HR Section of the DGPR Secretariat, the Inspectorate General, together with the HR Bureau of the Secretariat General as supervisors, recommend making improvements in terms of employee competence by increasing training programs, work environment and career development that affect employee job satisfaction problems in the DGPR environment. 2021. Based on the data gap above, The author wants to examine the job satisfaction of employees in the Ministry of Finance with variables following the recommendations of the Inspectorate General and the Bureau of HR of the Secretariat General. It is hoped that the results can improve the level of job satisfaction of employees in the Ministry of Finance by making improvements to deficiencies in the work environment variables and training and development career.

2. Materials and Methods

This study will analyze the effect of work environment and training on job satisfaction through career development as a mediation. This study describes the relationship between influencing and being influenced by the variables to be studied. This study uses a quantitative approach because the data used to analyze the relationship between variables are expressed by numbers or a numerical scale (Sekaran & Bougie, 2017).

In this research, Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) analysis technique was used using Partial Least Square (PLS). Herman OA Wold first developed PLS in the field of econometrics. According to (Ghozali, 2014), the PLS (Partial Least Square) approach is distributor free (does not assume certain data, can be nominal, category, ordinal, interval and ratio), and PLS (Partial Least Square) uses a bootstrapping method or random multiplication in which an assumption of normality will not be a problem.

3. Results and Discussions

Effect of Work Environment on Job Satisfaction (Hypothesis 1)

Based on the study results, it is known that there is an influence of the work environment on job satisfaction. This is because the value of t count $>$ t table ($6.424 > 1.96$) or P values $<$ 0.05 ($0.000 < 0.05$), so H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted. A positive coefficient value means that the effect is

positive. That is, if the work environment increases, job satisfaction also increases. Thus the first hypothesis, which states "There is an influence of the work environment on job satisfaction", is proven and can be declared accepted.

The results of the analysis of the description of the work environment variables in the previous sub-chapter show that the synergy culture indicators are part of the non-physical work environment. The employee relationship is very helpful for coordination between departments with an average value of 4.16. This can be interpreted that in the DJPPR environment as the object of research, organizational culture in the form of synergy has so far been carried out and is quite helpful in achieving organizational goals and has a positive effect on job satisfaction. Previous research conducted by (Lumintang et al., 2019) shows that the physical work environment has a positive effect on job satisfaction by proving the results of the t-test, which obtained t count $X_1 = 7.588$ accepted at a significance level of 5%. The physical work environment and non-physical work environment together positively affect job satisfaction. This is evident from the results of the F test, which obtained an F count of 87.424, which was accepted at a significance level of 5%.

Effect of Work Environment on Career Development (Hypothesis 2)

Based on the study results, it is known that there is an influence of the work environment on career development. This is because the value of t count $>$ t table ($3.244 > 1.96$) or P values $<$ 0.05 ($0.001 < 0.05$), so H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted. A positive coefficient value means that the effect is positive. That is, if the work environment increases, career development also increases. Thus the second hypothesis, which states, "There is an influence of the work environment on career development", is proven and can be declared accepted.

In the analysis of the previous description, it was found that the average value of the indicators of the question of synergy culture helping coordination between sections was 4.16. This shows that the non-physical work environment in the form of relationships between employees is needed as a supporting partner and positively affects employee career development. To develop a career, an employee must be able to work together in the form of synergy with other employees.

The results of this study are in line with the theory of obstacle regulation in a work environment that is part of action regulation, as stated by Lukas Windlinger (Meulenbroek & Danivska, 2021), which states that the risk of work assignments in the form of work overload in a social work environment that can occur suddenly will hinder the implementation of tasks and social-environmental relations between employees which affect social relations in the work environment and employee career development.

In line with the results in this study, previous research conducted by (Maulidya & Surabagiarta, 2020) on several State Civil Apparatus (ASN) employees, the results show that from the results of the hypothesis test, the t-count value for the work environment variable is 2,506 with a significance value of 0.016 ($0.016 < 0.05$) which indicates that the work environment has a significant effect on career development. The implication of previous research shows that organizations must pay attention to the work environment because it will affect employees at work. A comfortable work environment will make employees work well and as much as possible with the hope that employees can develop their careers to the fullest.

Effect of Training on Career Development (Hypothesis 3)

Based on the study results, it is known that there is an effect of training on career development. This is because the value of t arithmetic $>$ t table ($4.983 > 1.96$) or P values $<$ 0.05 ($0.000 < 0.05$), so H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted. A positive coefficient value means that the effect is positive. That is, if training increases, career development also increases. Thus the third hypothesis, which states,

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'there is an effect of training on career development', is proven and can be declared accepted.

The data obtained in the analysis of the description of this study indicate that the indicators of the training material provided are in accordance with the training objectives on the training variable, having an average value of 4.11 higher than the others. This indicates that the indicators of the material given in each training in This research are in accordance with the objectives of the training. The description analysis shows that the fulfilment of training needs will have a positive effect on employee career development.

Effect of Training on Job Satisfaction (Hypothesis 4)

Based on the study results, it is known that there is an effect of training on job satisfaction. This is because the value of $t_{\text{arithmetic}} > t_{\text{table}}$ ($5.724 > 1.96$) or $P \text{ values} < 0.05$ ($0.000 < 0.05$), so H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted. A positive coefficient value means that the effect is positive. That is, if training increases, job satisfaction also increases. Thus the fourth hypothesis, which states, "There is an effect of training on job satisfaction", is proven and can be declared accepted.

The highest average value on the training variable is found in the indicator of the suitability of the material to the training objectives, which is 4.11. This shows that the fulfilment of employee training in terms of the suitability of the material to the training objectives at DJPPR has so far been fulfilled and has a positive relationship with job satisfaction.

The results of this study are directly proportional to the results of several previous studies, including research conducted at The British Household Panel Survey by (Tabvuma et al., 2015), which shows that training has a positive relationship to employee job satisfaction. This study also suggests that the effect of training on job satisfaction is more found in government organizations when compared to private organizations. When viewed from the characteristics of respondents by gender, the level of job satisfaction of female employees is greater than that of male employees. Training research was conducted in *The British Household Panel Survey* regarding the type of training, location of training, duration of training and support from the organizers on the level of employee job satisfaction. The conclusion of research conducted by (Tabvuma et al., 2015) shows that the variable training hypothesis is positively related to the level of employee job satisfaction.

Based on the results of the study, it is known that there is an effect of career development on job satisfaction. This is because the value of $t_{\text{count}} > t_{\text{table}}$ ($2.899 > 1.96$) or $P \text{ values} < 0.05$ ($0.004 < 0.05$), so H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted. A positive coefficient value means that the effect is positive. That is, if career development increases, job satisfaction also increases. Thus the fifth hypothesis, which states, "There is an effect of career development on job satisfaction." is proven and can be declared acceptable.

From the data from the analysis of career development variable descriptions, it shows that the indicator of promoting employees is the right decision for the organization and getting an average value of 4.04, which indicates that promoting employees carried out at the DJPPR is objective in accordance with applicable regulations and in accordance with employee expectations.

The results of other studies that are in line with this study were carried out by (Pich & Fendy, 2021). In the fourth hypothesis, it is proven that the research results show a positive relationship between the influence of career development on the level of employee job satisfaction. The results of this study provide information that employee job satisfaction is obtained when employees get promotions at work. This study also shows that career development has an effect on job satisfaction, 38.7% greater than the effect of career development on employee performance.

Effect of Work Environment on Job Satisfaction through Career Development (Hypothesis 6)

Based on the results of the study, it is known that the work environment has an effect on job satisfaction through career development. This is based on the Indirect effect test. The P-value is less than 0.05 ($0.016 < 0.05$). Thus the sixth hypothesis, which states "Work environment affects job satisfaction through career development", is proven and can be declared accepted. The results of the analysis of the description of indicators of cooperative co-workers as a work environment variable with an average value of 3.98 show that colleagues in the DJPPR unit are very competent to support other employees in a non-physical work environment to achieve organizational goals.

The social work environment resulting from employee work experience and support from partners and superiors in the form of support partners will increase job satisfaction because the non-physical work environment will support the career development of an employee for the promotion process at a career level and result in improved income as an indicator of job satisfaction. (Athanasou, 2008). Interpersonal relationships in the work environment, which are reflected in the career development process through counselling activities, will affect employee job satisfaction (Brown, 2012)

Effect of Training on Job Satisfaction through Career Development (Hypothesis 7)

Based on the research results, it is known that training has an effect on job satisfaction through career development. This is based on the Indirect effect test. The P-value is less than 0.05 ($0.014 < 0.05$). Thus, the seventh hypothesis, which states "Training affects job satisfaction through career development", is proven and can be declared accepted.

The results of the analysis of the description of the material training indicators have been in accordance with the training objectives on the training variable, getting an average value of 4.11. This shows that so far, the material presented in training at DJPPR has been in accordance with the training objectives. One of the purposes of fulfilling the training is to use it as a means of employee career development which indirectly has a positive effect on job satisfaction.

In the theory of organizational psychologists, it is characterized by training aimed at employee career development through counselling methods to meet employee job satisfaction in relation to the psychological health of workers (Fernandes, 2001). Meanwhile, according to Hite and Mcdonald (Saira et al., 2020), when labour mobility increases due to the influence of globalization developments, various types of training are urgently needed for human resource development professionals so that the expected career can be achieved which will ultimately affect the level of employee job satisfaction.

A study (Anggita & Purba, 2015) examined the mediating variable of career development on the influence of training variables on job satisfaction at the PLN (Persero) Central Office. Job satisfaction, but through career development mediation. From the analysis of data processing, it was found that the calculation of the training variable has a significant indirect effect on job satisfaction through career development mediation with a coefficient of 0.2577 and a value of 0.0053. The value of R square is 0.1093 or 10.93%, and the rest is explained by other variables outside the research model.

4. Conclusion

The entire empirical model in this study was tested using the Structural Equation Model (SEM) analysis technique using *partial Least Square* (PLS), and the results are in accordance with the theory and previous research. The conclusions of the results of the thesis research are as follows;

1. The work environment has a positive effect on job satisfaction. This shows that if the work environment increases, then job satisfaction also increases. The results of the descriptive analysis of this study indicate that the synergy relationship between employees is an indicator of the work environment that needs to be maintained and even enhanced by a synergy culture that has been part of the non-physical work environment at DJPPR as a form of coordination between departments to achieve the vision and mission that has been set and fulfil job satisfaction. employees in terms of the work environment.

2. The work environment has a positive effect on career development. Namely, if the work environment increases, career development also increases. These results provide information that the information technology service facilities provided by DJPPR are very important in supporting business processes, especially during the pandemic. The Secretariat, as the unit in charge of information technology services, should always monitor this service to make it easier for employees to access information and complete work that supports their career development.
3. Training has a positive effect on career development. That is, if training increases, career development also increases. These results indicate that the training materials that have been provided at each training implementation have been in accordance with the training objectives. This is intended to support the career development of employees in meeting training needs.
4. Training has a positive effect on job satisfaction. That is, if training increases, job satisfaction also increases. These results indicate that the training objectives are clearly structured so that they are easy to understand. This makes it easier for prospective trainees to decide to take part in training which will ultimately fulfil employee job satisfaction with the implementation of the training.
5. Career development has a positive effect on job satisfaction; namely, if career development increases, job satisfaction also increases. These results provide information that promoting an employee is a very appropriate decision for the organization after going through a series of objective and accountable processes that will ultimately affect the level of employee job satisfaction.
6. The work environment has a positive effect on job satisfaction through career development. These results provide information that the work that is the responsibility of the employee can be completed properly. This is because, at the beginning of each year, there will be a discussion on the preparation of a performance contract which becomes an agreement between the employee and his immediate supervisor. The relationship between superiors and subordinates is part of a social work environment that will always support employee career development which will ultimately meet the level of job satisfaction.
7. Training has a positive effect on job satisfaction through career development. These results provide information that the training program held with partners as well as the Financial Education and Training Agency presents teachers who are competent in their fields, master the material and are able to convey the material well to trainee employees to meet training needs in order to develop careers in organizations that are will ultimately have an impact on employee job satisfaction.

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